

Implementation of temperature dependent corrections to the overlap functions of CHM15k ALC in the EPROFILE processing chain.

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Introduction

In the CHM15k ALC instrument the laser and receiving telescope are positioned not coaxially, with the laser being situated to one side of the telescope. Because of this spatial offset, the laser does not enter the field of view of the telescope for some distance above the instrument. Below this height the instrument will receive no signal from the laser. The telescope field of view forms a cone which spreads out with distance from the lidar (see fig. 1). Similarly, the laser also has some small divergence, and also spreads out with increasing height. When the two cones start to intersect the instrument will begin to receive backscattered laser light. The signal strength will continue to increase until the cone of the laser is completely within the field of view of the lidar; this region is known as the overlap region (e.g. Wandinger, Ansmann, 2002). Within this region the effects of atmospheric constituents on the backscatter signal are masked by the overlap effect. For the CHM15k the height of full overlap is nominally $\approx 250\text{m}$ for a perfectly aligned system. However, in practice the full overlap height can be much higher due to unavoidable alignment errors and due to the lidar optics. In most situations the lidar products above the overlap height are not affected. However, in some optical depth calculations for elastic only retrievals, the lidar ratio is fixed by matching the height integrated lidar extinction profile to the optical depth as measured by a sun-photometer. If the lower few hundreds of meters of the lidar extinction profile are missing due to the overlap effect, then the lidar ratio and subsequent products, such as mass concentration estimates, will have additional errors introduced. It is therefore desirable to correct for the overlap effect using an overlap function. This can be calculated analytically by considering the geometry of the system (e.g. Stelmaszczyk et al., 2005), or, for Raman lidar, it can be determined numerically using experimental data as in Wandinger, Ansmann (2002). For the CHM15k, the manufacturer provides an instrument specific overlap function, determined using a reference instrument for which the overlap function is well known.

As with any lidar system, temperature fluctuations within a CHM15k can introduce small geometric changes, and induce stresses in the optical elements, which all add up to significant fluctuations in the requirements of the overlap corrections (e.g. Campbell et al., 2002; Welton and Campbell, 2002). Hervo et al. 2016 provide an empirical method for correcting the CHM15k overlap function for temperature effects. This method is based on the data itself and does not require any onsite intervention or onsite measurement. It is therefore ideal for implementation across a large network of CHM15k instruments.

Among other activities, the EUMETMET funded EPROFILE program coordinates the production and exchange of ALC measurements of attenuated backscatter across

Europe and includes the processing and cataloguing of data from hundreds of ALCs, including 143 CHM15k instruments. The aim of the activity described in this report and funded by a virtual mobility grant (VMG) within the PROBE cost action, was to produce a set of documented and deployable Python code that could be integrated into the routine EPROFILE processing of CHM15k data to calculate and then apply the overlap function temperature corrections described in Hervo et al. 2016.

Pre-existing and new code

Computer code written in MATLAB by Maxime Hervo and Yann Poltera at MeteoSwiss pre-exists this VMG activity and required translation in Python and refactoring into an object-oriented format before it could be deployed with the EPROFILE processing chain. This was the aim of this VMG activity, and the scientific basis for the calculation of the temperature corrections is unchanged from that provided by Hervo et al. 2016.

As described in Hervo et al. 2016 the MATLAB code results in corrected overlap functions calculated using only data profiles carefully screened using an advanced quality control algorithm. An addition to the MATLAB code is a module written by Melania Van Hove to screen a time series of the corrected overlap functions and temperature models themselves (over a full sample of the temperature range the instrument is subjected to) and apply strict quality controls. This allows the automation of the whole process.

The result of this processing is a temperature model that can be used to correct each profile of CHM15k data using equations 1 through 3:

$$\Re l_{diff}(R) = a(R) \times T + b(R) \tag{1}$$

$$O_{corr}(R) = \frac{100 \times O_{Ref}(R)}{\Re l_{diff}(R) + 100} \tag{2}$$

$$\beta_{corrected}(R) = \beta(R) \times \frac{O_{Ref}(R)}{O_{corr}(R)} \tag{3}$$

Where a and b are the coefficients of the temperature model, R is range, T is the temperature reported by the CHM15k, O_{Ref} is the reference overlap function used in calculating the temperature model, O_{corr} is the temperature corrected overlap function and β is the attenuated backscatter profile.

This work has now mostly been completed and a working set of code is available here https://github.com/martin-obs/OVERLAP_PROBE_EPROFILE, and some documentation here <https://overlap-probe-eprofile.readthedocs.io/en/latest/>. Please note that at the

time of writing the documentation is in a preliminary form and continues to be updated.

/home/vam/L1_FILES/0-20000-0-10395/2022/07/L1_0-20000-0-10395_020220705.nc

Figure 1

EPROFILE processing structure

The processing and storage processing within EPROFILE are shared between MeteoSwiss and the UK Met Office data hub. Figure 2 shows a conceptual diagram of the EPROFILE data flow and processing chain. The yellow rectangles indicate processes conducted by MeteoSwiss, and the the green rectangles indicate processes conducted within the UK Met Office. The rectangle highlighted by red box A in fig. 2 indicates where the overlap correction code is now implemented at MeteoSwiss within the “overlap service”. Overlap temperature corrections are calculated yearly for each CHM15k, or when there is a change to a particular instrument, such as a change to the optics or laser modules. The new temperature models are then transmitted to the Met Office data hub where they will be applied to the data, along with the calibration, in the L1 to L2 processing (red box B in fig. 1).

The functionality to apply the temperature models is being added to the L1 to L2 processing, and will be ready by June 2024. After this change the “attenuated backscatter” variable reported in the EPROFILE L2 CHM15k data files will be overlap

temperature corrected. The exact model (a and b coefficients from eqn.1) and reference overlap function used to calculate the temperature model will also be included in the L2 file in the event that an advanced user wishes to remove the correction for any reason.

Summary

As a result of this VMG activity a new set of documented and deployable Python code is publicly available which will calculate temperature correction models for CHM15k data. The code is now implemented with the EPROFILE processing chain and will soon be applied in the L2 data files.